

BUKHARA IS THE COUNTRY OF GREAT INDIVIDUALS AND SAINTS.

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Annotation: Bukhara is one of the ancient cities of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the administrative, economic and cultural center of Bukhara region. It was one of the largest shopping malls on the Great Silk Road. It is located in the southwest of Uzbekistan, in the lower reaches of the Zarafshan River. The tenth-century historian Muhammad Narshahi's History of Bukhara provides information about Bukhara. Coins found in Bukhara testify to the development of trade and commodity relations. Depending on the coins, it is possible to see the change of the ruling dynasties, the names of the rulers, the naming of titles, the symbols of the dynasty - the emblem and other images. This article provides general information, opinions and comments about individuals and saints born and educated in Bukhara.

Keywords: Bukhara, great scholars, saints, Abu Ali Ibn Sino, Imam al-Bukhari, historical works, artistic and scientific heritage.

Bukhara is one of the major centers of science, spirituality and enlightenment. Since March 1996, the Bukhara regional center of the Samarkand branch of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan has been operating. In October 1997, the 2500th anniversary of the city of Bukhara was widely celebrated in Uzbekistan. Bukhara is one of the four cities in the Islamic world. In the East, it has long been said that "Samarkand is the land of beauty, the power of Bukhara is Islam."

Many poets, scientists, thinkers and mystics, travelers, ambassadors, historians and geographers of the world have created valuable works in honor of Bukhara Sharif. Between 1103 and 1389, the seven nobles, who spread the fame of Bukhara throughout the Islamic world and around the world, ruled one after another, in the twelfth and fourteenth centuries, and did very good deeds. It is known that this period marked the end of Mongol oppression and tyranny in Movarounnahr and Khorasan, in the vast and vast Muslim region of Central Asia, and in the great spiritual and cultural home of the great and powerful Timuridempire. was a period of decay.

In the third (ninth century), which was a golden age in the development of the science of hadith, great achievements were made in the study of hadith. Imam al-Bukhari, who was awarded the honorary title of "Amir al-Mu'minin in the science of hadith," is a great scholar of special interest. His full name was Imam al-Bukhari and he was born on July 20, 810 in Bukhara. Unlike many other scholars, al-Bukhari's date of birth is clearly stated because his father, Ismail, was one of the most learned men of his time, and the paper on which he wrote his son's birthday in his own handwriting was made available to contemporary scholars, and there is no doubt about its accuracy. Al-Bukhari's father died when he was young and he was raised by his mother. From an early age, he was intelligent, sharp-witted, and passionate about enlightenment, and studied various sciences, especially hadith, with great interest. Most of Imam al-Bukhari's life was spent in exile.

Imam al-Bukhari was not only a great scholar, but also distinguished by his good manners, humanity, kindness, generosity and unparalleled generosity. He is also known for his sharp wit and strong memory. Sources say that al-Bukhari memorized about 600,000 hadiths. After returning from abroad, Imam al-Bukhari taught hadith to many students and scholars in his native Bukhara. Many respected him, but some jealous, malicious people could not see al-Bukhari. As a result, al-Bukhari's relationship with the Emir of Bukhara, Khalid ibn Ahmad az-Zuhali, was severed due to jealousy. The reason for this was that the Amir asked the scholar to come to him and read the books Al-Jame 'as-Sahih and At-Tarikh. But al-Bukhari said, "I do not despise science and take it to the gates of the rulers. Whoever needs knowledge should seek it." But Allah will forgive me on the Day of Judgment for not hiding knowledge and spending it on the Taliban."

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Narshakhi's book focuses on the development of the Bukhara oasis, hunting, fishing and agriculture, from the establishment of such ancient villages as Numijkat, Poykand, Afshona, Varakhsha, Romiton, Vardona to the rise of Bukhara. important historical events. The book contains interesting information about the establishment of the Arab caliphate in Central Asia, the spread of Islam, the crisis of fire and related cultural life, Muqanna - the movement of "white-clad", the Samanid state administration, cultural structures. It contains information on the economic, social and cultural life of Bukhara, in particular, monetary relations, the system of tax collection.

One of the great thinkers who brought the culture of the peoples of Central Asia to the forefront of world culture in the Middle Ages was Abu Ali Husayn ibn Abdullah ibn Sina, better known in Europe as Avicenna. Ibn Sina was born in the village of Afshana in Bukhara in the month of Safar in 980, in the family of an official. In 986, Ibn Sina's family moved to Bukhara, and from that time on, the young Hussein began to receive basic education and study science. His youth dates back to the last years of Samanid rule, particularly during the reign of Noah II ibn Mansur Samanid (976-997).

Ibn Sina was talented, had a strong memory and a sharp mind, so he quickly mastered the sciences known in his time. At the age of 10, he memorized the Qur'an from cover to cover. At the age of 13, he began to study elementary mathematics, logic, jurisprudence, and philosophy. Despite his young age, Ibn Sina studied philosophy under Abu Abdullah al-Natili, and Hasan ibn Nuh al-Qumri studied medicine in detail, and gradually became a doctor. At the age of 16-17, Ibn Sina became known as a famous physician and judge. In 1000, Ibn Sina left Bukhara and went to Khorezm, one of the centers of culture, where he was admitted to the academy of the ruler of Khorezm Ali ibn Mamun, which united the leading scholars of his time.

The total number of Ibn Sina's works exceeds 450, but only about 160 have survived. Many of his pamphlets were lost due to urban migration, wars, palace riots, and various disasters. In

many sources, IbnSina is interpreted primarily as a physician, although medicine is one of the most important of his scientific fields.

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